

Certifying Quantum Optimization and Circuit Cutting by Using Quantum–Classical Moment Duality

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Abstract

We establish a direct quantum–classical duality based on the degree-2 Sum-of-Squares (SoS) semidefinite programming cone: the matrix of two-qubit Pauli- Z correlation functions obtained from *any* quantum state ρ is automatically a feasible point of the classical Goemans–Williamson (GW) relaxation. This observation provides a universal “safety net” for quantum optimization algorithms: applying GW random hyperplane rounding to the quantum-driven moment matrix yields a certified expected cut value $\mathbb{E}[\text{Cut}] \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} \langle \mathcal{H} \rangle_{\rho}$, valid for every state produced by variational algorithms such as QAOA or the Variational Quantum Power Method (VQPM), regardless of convergence quality. We further show that the same moment matrix reveals the tensor-product structure of the underlying unitary circuit, enabling a polynomial-time, correlation-based circuit cutting procedure with rigorous error bounds. The framework is validated numerically on Max-Cut instances for variational quantum algorithms and on random states for circuit cutting, demonstrating that the cheap two-point correlation data are sufficient to locate near-optimal bipartitions and that the theoretical error bounds hold in practice.

Keywords— Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm, Variational Quantum Power Method, Sum-of-Squares Hierarchy, Semidefinite Programming, Quantum-Classical Duality, Quantum Circuit Cutting.

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1 Introduction

Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimization (QUBO) is a unifying framework for a vast class of NP-hard problems, and its mapping to the quantum Ising Hamiltonian has driven the development of numerous quantum optimization algorithms. Because exact solutions remain out of reach in the worst case, a great deal of effort has been devoted to convex relaxations that can provide rigorous performance bounds. In the classical domain, the degree-2 Sum-of-Squares (SoS) relaxation—conceptually equivalent to the Goemans–Williamson (GW) semidefinite program [1]—guarantees an approximation ratio $\alpha_{\text{GW}} \approx 0.87856$ for Max-Cut by optimizing over a symmetric pseudo-expectation matrix $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$ constrained to the positive semidefinite cone $\mathcal{S}_{\text{SoS}} = \{Y \succeq 0, Y_{i,i} = 1\}$. The SoS hierarchy was later systematised by Parrilo [2] and Lasserre [3], and has become a central tool in the analysis of approximation algorithms [4].

A key observation of the present work is that the matrix of two-qubit Pauli- Z correlations obtained from *any* quantum state ρ automatically furnishes a feasible point in this classical cone. Concretely, define the mapping Φ that extracts single- and two-qubit expectation values:

$$Y_{\text{quantum}} = \Phi(\rho) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \langle Z_1 \rangle_\rho & \cdots & \langle Z_n \rangle_\rho \\ \langle Z_1 \rangle_\rho & 1 & \cdots & \langle Z_1 Z_n \rangle_\rho \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \langle Z_n \rangle_\rho & \langle Z_n Z_1 \rangle_\rho & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\langle O \rangle_\rho = \text{Tr}(\rho O)$. As we prove in Theorem 2.1, Y_{quantum} is always positive semidefinite and has unit diagonal, i.e. $Y_{\text{quantum}} \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{SoS}}$, independently of the origin of ρ . The physical density matrix therefore acts as an *active optimization proxy* inside the continuous geometry of the semidefinite cone. In this paper we exploit this quantum–classical moment duality for two concrete and important purposes: *certification of quantum Max-Cut solvers* and *correlation-based circuit cutting*.

Certification of quantum Max-Cut. Because Y_{quantum} is feasible for the degree-2 SoS SDP, we may apply the classical Goemans–Williamson random hyperplane rounding directly to it. This yields an expected cut weight

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\text{Cut}] &= \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{\arccos((Y_{\text{quantum}})_{ij})}{\pi} \\ &\geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{1 - (Y_{\text{quantum}})_{ij}}{2} = \alpha_{\text{GW}} \langle \mathcal{H} \rangle_\rho, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{H} is the Ising Max-Cut Hamiltonian and $E_\rho = \langle \mathcal{H} \rangle_\rho$ is its quantum expectation value. Since the optimal SDP value SDP^* upper-bounds the true maximum cut, we obtain the certified relative bound

$$\frac{\mathbb{E}[\text{Cut}]}{\text{MaxCut}} \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} \frac{E_\rho}{\text{SDP}^*} = \alpha_{\text{GW}} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta}{\text{SDP}^*}\right), \quad \Delta = \text{SDP}^* - E_\rho \geq 0, \quad (3)$$

which cleanly separates the classical integrality gap from the quantum optimisation deficit Δ . Crucially, this bound applies to *any* state produced by a variational algorithm—including QAOA, VQE, and the Variational

Quantum Power Method (VQPM)—thereby providing a universal “safety net” that decouples algorithmic convergence from performance certification.

Correlation-based circuit cutting. The same moment matrix Y_{quantum} carries structural information about the quantum state’s entanglement and can therefore diagnose factorisability of the underlying unitary U . If U admits a tensor-product decomposition $U = A_S \otimes B_T$, the output state $|\psi\rangle = U|0\rangle^{\otimes n}$ factorises, and the connected correlation

$$C_{ij} = \langle Z_i Z_j \rangle - \langle Z_i \rangle \langle Z_j \rangle \quad (4)$$

vanishes for all $i \in S, j \in T$. Consequently, the graph built by thresholding $|C_{ij}| > \varepsilon$ is disconnected, and its connected components yield candidate partitions. We further give a purity-based criterion that is both necessary and sufficient for exact factorisation, and show that minimising the absolute connected correlation across a cut via a weighted minimum-cut problem extends the method to near-product states. This provides a geometry-agnostic, polynomial-time procedure for circuit cutting that works directly from physically measurable two-point correlations, circumventing the NP-complete overhead of finding optimal cut configurations [5]. We also provide a rigorous error bound: for any bipartition (S, T) , the distance between the original state and the best product state is bounded by $\sqrt{I(S:T)}$, where $I(S:T)$ is the quantum mutual information; when the state is prepared from a single probe, this translates into an error bound for the reconstructed product unitary on that input, and a global bound can be obtained by analysing the Choi state of U .

Relation to prior work. Classical semidefinite relaxations for Max-Cut were pioneered by Goemans and Williamson [1] and later embedded in the sum-of-squares (SoS) hierarchy [2–4, 6]. In the quantum domain, the interplay between semidefinite programming and quantum mechanics has been investigated from multiple perspectives. *Quantum SoS and NPA hierarchies.* Navascués, Pironio, and Acín introduced the celebrated NPA hierarchy [7, 8], an infinite sequence of SDPs that characterizes quantum correlations and provides systematic tests for ruling out non-quantum behaviors. Hastings and O’Donnell [9] optimized strongly interacting fermionic Hamiltonians using SoS, while Hastings [10] further developed field-theoretic techniques for the quantum SoS hierarchy, analyzing spin and fermion systems, critical phenomena, and nonlocal couplings in time. Subsequent work [11] revealed both limitations (a fragment of SoS cannot give the correct order-of-magnitude bound for the SYK model) and separations (a graph invariant $\Psi(G)$ can be strictly larger than the independence number), and defined the quantum knapsack problem. King et al. [12] combined SoS decompositions with spectral amplification to achieve a square-root improvement in system size for quantum simulation of the SYK model. Wang et al. [13] proposed a quantum metaheuristic for polynomial optimization based on SoS programming. Barak et al. [14] employed high-level SoS relaxations to address the best separable quantum state problem, actively searching for a rank-one matrix inside a subspace (i.e., a separable state). Watts et al. [15] introduced a non-commutative SoS hierarchy tailored to the swap operator algebra, leveraging representation theory of the symmetric group to derive exact relaxations for small Quantum Max-Cut instances and exact algebraic solutions for certain graph families. Our work shares the broad theme of embedding quantum observables into semidefinite relaxations, but the scope is fundamentally different: all these prior approaches actively construct problem-specific SDPs or use the hierarchy to solve an optimization, whereas we prove that the two-qubit Pauli- Z correlation matrix of *any* quantum state is automatically a feasible point of the classical degree-2 SoS cone, a universal structural fact that requires no hierarchy and no active SDP solving.

Quantum Max-Cut approximations. A parallel line of work addresses Quantum Max Cut (QMC), the problem of finding a high-energy state of the antiferromagnetic Heisenberg Hamiltonian $H = \sum_{ij} w_{ij}(I - X_i X_j - Y_i Y_j - Z_i Z_j)/4$. Gharibian and Parekh [16] gave almost-optimal classical approximation algorithms for QMC by relaxing to a level-2 quantum Lasserre SDP and rounding to product states; Parekh and Thompson [17] applied the level-2 quantum Lasserre hierarchy to obtain approximation guarantees. Subsequent improvements include SDP rounding to more general entangled states [17–19] and an optimal $1/2$ -approximation via product states [20]. Lee and Parekh [21] introduced a matching-based rounding of a level-2 SDP to a product of at most 2-qubit states, and Apte et al. [22] extended this by partially entangling matched qubit pairs. Takahashi et al. [23] developed an $SU(2)$ -symmetric SDP hierarchy that converges to the optimal QMC value at a finite level. These works address the *quantum* analogue of Max-Cut, where the Hamiltonian contains $XX + YY + ZZ$ terms, and they actively solve SDP relaxations to produce high-energy quantum states. Our contribution, by contrast, is a passive certificate for the *classical* Max-Cut problem: the

two-qubit Z -correlation matrix of any state (produced, e.g., by a variational algorithm) is already feasible for the classical SoS SDP, enabling GW rounding without solving any SDP. Here note that in a more general context, Brandão and Harrow [24] established that any quantum state on a lattice can be approximated by a product state with an error that scales with the mutual information across the cut. Their results provide rigorous foundations for the idea that low mutual information implies closeness to a product state—a fact we exploit directly in Theorem 4.1 and in our circuit-cutting error bounds.

Quantum algorithms for SDPs. Patti et al. [25] introduced a variational quantum algorithm for the Goemans–Williamson SDP that uses only $n + 1$ qubits and a constant number of circuit preparations, outperforming classical methods on GSet instances. Patel et al. [26] provided rigorous convergence guarantees for variational quantum SDP solvers for weakly constrained problems, and Chen et al. [27] proposed a slack-variable reformulation suited to near-term quantum devices. These methods aim to *solve* SDPs quantumly; our method uses the quantum device only to *produce* measurement data, with all optimization and rounding performed classically.

Approximability of local Hamiltonians. Gharibian and Kempe [28] showed that a broad class of QMA-hard problems can be approximated via polynomial-time quantum algorithms that embed quantum information into classical convex relaxations. While their approach relies on exhaustive sampling tailored to dense Hamiltonians, our contribution is a universal feasibility mapping into the SoS cone applicable to any quantum state, without assumptions on Hamiltonian density.

Circuit cutting and correlation-based partitioning. In circuit cutting, quasiprobabilistic decompositions [29, 30] and graph-combinatorial methods [5] have been proposed, but finding the optimal cut is NP-complete, and existing heuristics rely on geometry or brute-force search. Recent works [31, 32] have explored using mutual information and correlation-based criteria to identify low-entanglement partitions, and Bechtold et al. [33] studied patterns for quantum circuit cutting. Our contribution to this line is a concrete, polynomial-time procedure that extracts a near-optimal bipartition directly from the two-point Pauli- Z correlation matrix, with rigorous error bounds (Theorems 4.1 and 4.2), requiring no additional tomography beyond the measurements already performed for energy estimation.

Variational quantum algorithms. QAOA [34] and VQE [35] are the most studied variational quantum algorithms; their approximation ratios have been investigated [36–38] but are instance-dependent and often lack per-state guarantees. The Variational Quantum Power Method (VQPM) [39, 40] introduces a qubit-locking heuristic that accelerates convergence, yet no rigorous per-iteration certificate was available. Our work supplies exactly that: a universal certificate that holds for every state produced by these algorithms, decoupling convergence from certification.

In summary, while prior works either solve SDPs classically, solve SDPs quantumly, or use quantum states as oracles for high-order correlations, our contribution is the proof that the two-qubit Pauli- Z correlation matrix of *any* quantum state is itself a feasible point in the degree-2 SoS cone, establishing a direct quantum–classical moment dictionary. This yields (i) a universal performance certificate for Max-Cut via GW rounding, (ii) a correlation-based circuit cutting procedure with rigorous error bounds, and (iii) a detailed analysis of the certificate in VQPM including an energy-leakage bound under qubit locking.

2 Main Method: The Quantum–Classical Moment Dictionary

2.1 The Classical SoS Relaxation Space

Let $x \in \{-1, +1\}^n$ be a vector of classical spins. The degree-2 Sum-of-Squares (SoS) relaxation introduces a linear pseudo-expectation operator $\tilde{\mathbb{E}}[\cdot]$ that evaluates polynomials of degree ≤ 2 and organizes the values into a symmetric moment matrix $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$ indexed by the extended basis $[1, x_1, \dots, x_n]^T$:

$$Y_{0,0} = 1, \quad Y_{0,i} = \tilde{\mathbb{E}}[x_i], \quad Y_{i,j} = \tilde{\mathbb{E}}[x_i x_j] \quad (i, j \geq 1). \quad (5)$$

The relaxation enforces that Y belongs to the positive semidefinite cone with unit diagonal:

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{SoS}} = \{Y \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)} \mid Y \succeq 0, Y_{i,i} = 1 \forall i\}. \quad (6)$$

2.2 The Quantum Feasibility Mapping

Let $\rho \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H}_n)$ be a physically valid density operator on $\mathcal{H}_n = (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$. We define the mapping $\Phi : \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{H}_n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$ that extracts single- and two-qubit Pauli-Z expectation values:

$$Y_{\text{quantum}} = \Phi(\rho) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \langle Z_1 \rangle_\rho & \cdots & \langle Z_n \rangle_\rho \\ \langle Z_1 \rangle_\rho & 1 & \cdots & \langle Z_1 Z_n \rangle_\rho \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \langle Z_n \rangle_\rho & \langle Z_n Z_1 \rangle_\rho & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $\langle O \rangle_\rho = \text{Tr}(\rho O)$.

Theorem 2.1 (Rigorous Feasibility Retention). *For any quantum state ρ , the matrix $Y_{\text{quantum}} = \Phi(\rho)$ is a feasible point of the classical degree-2 SoS cone \mathcal{S}_{SoS} .*

Proof. We verify the two defining properties of \mathcal{S}_{SoS} .

1. **Diagonal normalization.** For every $i \geq 1$, $Y_{i,i} = \text{Tr}(\rho Z_i^2) = \text{Tr}(\rho I) = 1$, because $Z_i^2 = I$ and $\text{Tr}(\rho) = 1$.
2. **Positive semidefiniteness.** For an arbitrary vector $v = [v_0, v_1, \dots, v_n]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$, define the Hermitian observable $O_v = v_0 I + \sum_{i=1}^n v_i Z_i$. A direct computation yields

$$v^T Y_{\text{quantum}} v = \text{Tr}(\rho O_v^2). \quad (8)$$

Both ρ and O_v^2 are positive semidefinite (O_v is Hermitian, so its square is PSD), and the trace of the product of two PSD operators is non-negative [41]. Hence $v^T Y_{\text{quantum}} v \geq 0$.

Therefore $Y_{\text{quantum}} \succeq 0$ with $Y_{i,i} = 1$, i.e. $Y_{\text{quantum}} \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{SoS}}$. \square

Because the $n \times n$ submatrix M defined by $M_{ij} = \langle Z_i Z_j \rangle_\rho$ for $1 \leq i, j \leq n$ is a principal submatrix of Y_{quantum} , it inherits positive semidefiniteness and has unit diagonal. Consequently, M is a Gram matrix of unit vectors: there exist vectors $u_1, \dots, u_n \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $\langle u_i, u_j \rangle = M_{ij}$.

2.3 Performance Certificate for Max-Cut

The Max-Cut problem on a graph $G = (V, E)$ with edge weights $w_{ij} \geq 0$ is encoded in the Ising Hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} (I - Z_i Z_j), \quad (9)$$

whose expectation value in a state ρ is $E_\rho = \langle \mathcal{H} \rangle_\rho = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j)} w_{ij} (1 - \langle Z_i Z_j \rangle_\rho)$.

Theorem 2.2 (Performance Certificate). *Let ρ be any quantum state and $Y_{\text{quantum}} = \Phi(\rho)$. Applying Goemans–Williamson random hyperplane rounding [1] to the Gram vectors of the $n \times n$ correlation submatrix M yields a random cut \mathcal{C} whose expected weight satisfies*

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{weight}(\mathcal{C})] \geq \alpha_{GW} E_\rho, \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha_{GW} = \min_{0 \leq \theta \leq \pi} \frac{2\theta}{\pi(1 - \cos \theta)} \approx 0.87856$. Equivalently, the true approximation ratio is bounded by

$$\frac{\mathbb{E}[\text{weight}(\mathcal{C})]}{\text{MaxCut}} \geq \alpha_{GW} \frac{E_\rho}{SDP^*} = \alpha_{GW} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta}{SDP^*}\right), \quad \Delta = SDP^* - E_\rho \geq 0, \quad (11)$$

where SDP^* is the optimal value of the degree-2 SoS relaxation and Δ is the quantum optimization deficit.

Proof. Since $Y_{\text{quantum}} \in \mathcal{S}_{\text{SoS}}$ by Theorem 2.1, the Gram vectors u_i satisfy $\langle u_i, u_i \rangle = M_{ii} = 1$ and $\langle u_i, u_j \rangle = M_{ij} = \langle Z_i Z_j \rangle_\rho$. Random hyperplane rounding with a uniformly distributed unit vector $r \in \mathbb{R}^n$ assigns spin $+1$ to vertex i if $\langle u_i, r \rangle \geq 0$ and -1 otherwise. For an edge (i, j) , the probability that i and j receive opposite signs is exactly $\frac{\arccos(\langle u_i, u_j \rangle)}{\pi}$ [1]. Hence

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{weight}(\mathcal{C})] = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{\arccos(M_{ij})}{\pi}. \quad (12)$$

The Goemans–Williamson inequality $\frac{\arccos(z)}{\pi} \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} \frac{1-z}{2}$ holds for all $z \in [-1, 1]$. Substituting M_{ij} gives

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{weight}(\mathcal{C})] \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{1 - M_{ij}}{2} = \alpha_{\text{GW}} \langle \mathcal{H} \rangle_\rho = \alpha_{\text{GW}} E_\rho. \quad (13)$$

Finally, since $\text{MaxCut} \leq \text{SDP}^*$ (the continuous relaxation upper-bounds the discrete optimum), we obtain

$$\frac{\mathbb{E}[\text{weight}(\mathcal{C})]}{\text{MaxCut}} \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} \frac{E_\rho}{\text{SDP}^*} = \alpha_{\text{GW}} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta}{\text{SDP}^*}\right), \quad (14)$$

with $\Delta = \text{SDP}^* - E_\rho$. □

2.4 Universality of the Mapping

Theorems 2.1 and 2.2 rely on no property of ρ other than its being a valid density matrix. Hence they apply to *any* quantum state—produced by a variational circuit, a non-unitary operation, adiabatic evolution, or even a noisy measurement. The quantum–classical moment dictionary thus provides a universal post-processing protocol:

1. Measure the two-point Pauli- Z correlations $\langle Z_i Z_j \rangle_\rho$ (and single-qubit expectations $\langle Z_i \rangle_\rho$);
2. Assemble the moment matrix $Y_{\text{quantum}} = \Phi(\rho)$;
3. Apply Goemans–Williamson rounding to obtain the certified cut value

$$F(\rho) = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{\arccos((Y_{\text{quantum}})_{i,j})}{\pi}, \quad (15)$$

which satisfies $F(\rho) \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} E_\rho$.

Remarkably, $F(\rho)$ can be strictly larger than the raw energy expectation E_ρ , offering a means to refine performance bounds by directly optimizing the rounded objective rather than the energy. The following sections apply this framework to QAOA and VQPM.

3 Application to Variational Quantum Algorithms

Variational quantum algorithms are the leading paradigm for near-term quantum optimization. The Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) [34] and the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) [35] prepare parameterized trial states and measure expectation values, while the Variational Quantum Power Method (VQPM) [39, 40] mimics classical power iteration through repeated application of a non-unitary operator. A common shortcoming of these heuristics is the lack of rigorous per-state performance guarantees: QAOA bounds are instance-dependent and hold only at globally optimal parameters [36, 38], and VQPM convergence has been assessed empirically. In this section we show that any state produced by these algorithms yields a feasible moment matrix, and therefore a universal certification via Goemans–Williamson rounding. We illustrate the certificate on QAOA, and later on VQPM.

3.1 Certification of QAOA States

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph with nonnegative edge weights w_{ij} . The cost Hamiltonian for Max-Cut is

$$\mathcal{H}_C = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} (I - Z_i Z_j). \quad (16)$$

The standard $p=1$ QAOA circuit prepares the state

$$|\psi(\gamma, \beta)\rangle = e^{-i\beta H_M} e^{-i\gamma \mathcal{H}_C} |+\rangle^{\otimes n}, \quad (17)$$

with mixing Hamiltonian $H_M = \sum_{k=1}^n X_k$. From the two-point correlations $y_{ij}(\gamma, \beta) = \langle \psi(\gamma, \beta) | Z_i Z_j | \psi(\gamma, \beta) \rangle$ we construct the moment matrix Y_{quantum} as in Eq. (7). By Theorem 2.1 this matrix is feasible for the degree-2 SoS SDP, and Theorem 2.2 gives the certified expected cut

$$F(\gamma, \beta) = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{\arccos(y_{ij}(\gamma, \beta))}{\pi} \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} E_{\text{QAOA}}(\gamma, \beta), \quad (18)$$

where $E_{\text{QAOA}}(\gamma, \beta) = \sum w_{ij} \frac{1-y_{ij}}{2}$ is the raw energy expectation. The best bound achievable by this single-layer QAOA circuit is

$$\text{LB}_{\text{GW-QAOA}_1}(G) = \max_{\gamma, \beta} F(\gamma, \beta). \quad (19)$$

Notice that $F(\gamma, \beta)$ may be smaller than E_{QAOA} when the edge correlations are negative (as in typical Max-Cut instances); the certificate is still valid but not necessarily tighter than the energy. However, the bound is a *state-dependent geometric certificate* that holds for *any* parameter choice, not only at the global optimum. This decouples the performance guarantee from the classical optimizer’s convergence, providing a safety net even for noisy or early-terminated optimization.

Light-cone limitations of shallow QAOA. At depth $p = 1$, the Heisenberg evolution of a single-qubit observable is confined to a light-cone of radius 2: only qubits within graph distance 2 can be correlated. Consequently, the QAOA correlation functions—and hence the moment matrix—are blind to global graph cycles, which fundamentally limits the approximation ratio on sparse regular graphs (best known lower bound 0.692 for $p = 1$, 0.7559 for $p = 2$ on 3-regular graphs [34, 38]). Nevertheless, our certificate applies at every point in the parameter landscape, regardless of this locality obstruction.

3.2 Illustration: QAOA $p = 1$ on the 4-Cycle

We demonstrate the bound on the 4-cycle C_4 (unit edge weights). Numerical optimization of $F(\gamma, \beta)$ and $E_{\text{QAOA}}(\gamma, \beta)$ yields the same optimal angles $(\gamma^*, \beta^*) = (0.785, 0.393)$. At these angles the edge correlations are $y_{ij} = -0.5$ on all edges and 0 on non-edges. The moment matrix and the resulting values are

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -0.5 & 0 & -0.5 \\ 0 & -0.5 & 1 & -0.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -0.5 & 1 & -0.5 \\ 0 & -0.5 & 0 & -0.5 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

$$E_{\text{QAOA}} = 3.0, \quad F(\gamma^*, \beta^*) = 4 \cdot \frac{\arccos(-0.5)}{\pi} = 2.6667.$$

While $F < E_{\text{QAOA}}$, the certificate is respected: $2.6667 \geq 0.87856 \times 3.0 \approx 2.636$, so the rounded value safely lower-bounds the maximum cut (4). Figure 1 compares the optimization landscapes of F and E_{QAOA} .

QAOA $p=1$ on C_4 : GW-rounded bound vs. QAOA energy

Figure 1: Left: GW-rounded objective $F(\gamma, \beta)$. Middle: QAOA energy $E_{\text{QAOA}}(\gamma, \beta)$. Right: optimal values. The GW-rounded bound is lower than the energy, yet respects the α_{GW} guarantee.

Figure 2: Continuous optimization trajectory of $p=1$ QAOA on C_4 . The GW-rounded cut F_{GW} (blue) stays above the certified lower bound $\alpha_{\text{GW}} E_\rho$ (dashed) at all iterations, even when the raw energy is poor.

Dynamical trajectory. Figure 2 tracks a variational optimization of (γ, β) starting from random initial parameters. At early iterations, when the raw quantum energy E_ρ is low (highly sub-optimal), the classical rounding F_{GW} remains strictly above the analytic floor $\alpha_{\text{GW}}E_\rho$. This illustrates that the certificate is active throughout the entire optimization, not only at convergence. Even if the optimizer stalls or the hardware introduces noise, the measured two-point correlations can still be used to produce a guaranteed cut.

This example underscores that the moment-matrix certificate is a *per-state* safety net, completely decoupled from the classical optimization dynamics. The next section applies the same duality to VQPM, where qubit-locking further highlights the robustness of the framework.

3.3 Application to VQPM

The Variational Quantum Power Method (VQPM) [39, 40] is a hybrid quantum–classical algorithm that seeks the ground state of a QUBO problem by mimicking classical power iteration. Unlike QAOA, which alternates fixed unitaries, VQPM repeatedly applies a non-unitary operator and reinitialises the quantum state via single-qubit rotation gates whose parameters are updated from measurement outcomes. Its central heuristic, *qubit locking*, collapses a qubit to a definite computational basis state once its probability imbalance exceeds a threshold. We first recall the classical and quantum power iterations that motivate the algorithm, then describe the Max-Cut encoding, the VQPM circuit, the locking mechanism, and finally how the moment-matrix safety net certifies its performance.

3.3.1 Classical and quantum power iteration

Let \mathcal{H} be a Hermitian matrix with eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N$ and eigenvectors $|1\rangle, \dots, |N\rangle$. Assume a unique dominant eigenvalue $|\lambda_d| > |\lambda_s|$ for all $s \neq d$. The classical power method iterates

$$|\psi_k\rangle = \frac{\mathcal{H}^k |\psi_0\rangle}{\|\mathcal{H}^k |\psi_0\rangle\|}, \quad (21)$$

which converges to $|d\rangle$ exponentially in k provided $\langle d|\psi_0\rangle \neq 0$. For QUBO matrices of dimension 2^n explicit powers are intractable, motivating a quantum version.

The quantum power iteration [42] uses a control qubit and the unitary $\mathcal{U} = e^{i\mathcal{H}}$, which shares the eigenbasis of \mathcal{H} . Starting from an initial state $|\psi_0\rangle$ (typically the equal superposition), the circuit prepares $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes |\psi_0\rangle$, applies \mathcal{U} conditioned on the control, and a final Hadamard on the control, giving

$$\frac{1}{2} \left[|0\rangle \otimes (I + \mathcal{U}) |\psi_0\rangle + |1\rangle \otimes (I - \mathcal{U}) |\psi_0\rangle \right]. \quad (22)$$

Post-selecting on the control being $|0\rangle$ implements $I + \mathcal{U}$; on $|1\rangle$ implements $I - \mathcal{U}$. Repeating k times yields

$$|\psi_k\rangle \propto (I \pm \mathcal{U})^k |\psi_0\rangle. \quad (23)$$

The eigenvalues of $I \pm \mathcal{U}$ are $1 \pm e^{i\lambda_j}$. For $I - \mathcal{U}$ the magnitude is $|1 - e^{i\lambda_j}| = 2|\sin(\lambda_j/2)|$, maximal when $\lambda_j = \pi$; thus if the ground state phase is shifted near π , the iteration $(I - \mathcal{U})^k$ amplifies the ground state. The success probability after k steps scales as R^{2k} with $R = \sin(\lambda_s/2)/\sin(\lambda_d/2)$ (for $I - \mathcal{U}$). For small gaps, many iterations are needed, motivating a variational shortcut.

3.3.2 Max-Cut as a QUBO and unitary encoding

For a graph $G = (V, E)$ with edge weights w_{ij} , the Max-Cut objective $\text{Cut}(x) = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij}(x_i \neq x_j)$ with $x_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is equivalent to minimising the QUBO Hamiltonian

$$H(x) = \sum_i q_{ii}x_i + \sum_{i < j} q_{ij}x_ix_j, \quad (24)$$

with $q_{ii} = \sum_j w_{ij}$, $q_{ij} = -2w_{ij}$ ($i < j$). Mapping $x_i \mapsto (1 - Z_i)/2$ yields the Ising Hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_i b_i Z_i + \sum_{i < j} J_{ij} Z_i Z_j + \text{const}, \quad (25)$$

with coefficients derived from Q . All terms commute, so the unitary

$$U = e^{i\mathcal{H}} \quad (26)$$

is diagonal: $U|x\rangle = e^{i\phi(x)}|x\rangle$ with $\phi(x) = \sum_{i \leq j} q_{ij}x_i x_j$ (up to a constant). The ground state of \mathcal{H} corresponds to the maximum cut, and is the eigenvector of U with the largest eigenphase. By scaling the QUBO matrix so that the phases lie in $[-\pi/4, \pi/4]$ and shifting by $\pi/4$, the ground state phase is placed near $\pi/2$, making $I - U$ have a dominant eigenvalue.

3.3.3 VQPM circuit and reinitialisation

To keep the circuit shallow, VQPM does not iterate a full quantum state. Instead, after each application of $I - U$ the system is measured, and a new product state is prepared using single-qubit $R_y(\theta)$ gates whose parameters are set from the previous measurement statistics. Concretely, at iteration k we start from a product state $|\text{in}\rangle$ and compute

$$|\psi_0\rangle = \frac{|\text{in}\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |\psi_1\rangle = -U|\psi_0\rangle, \quad |\psi_{\text{final}}\rangle = \frac{|\psi_0\rangle + |\psi_1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \propto (I - U)|\text{in}\rangle. \quad (27)$$

The negative sign encodes the $I - U$ operator. The state is normalised, measured in the computational basis, and the resulting single-qubit probabilities determine the R_y angles for the next iteration. For n qubits the unitary U requires $O(n^2)$ phase gates. The initial state is the equal superposition $|\psi_0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n}} \sum_{j=0}^{2^n-1} |j\rangle$.

3.3.4 Qubit locking

After each iteration, VQPM measures each qubit and computes the probability difference

$$\Delta P^{(i)} = |P_0^{(i)} - P_1^{(i)}| = |\text{Tr}(\rho Z_i)|. \quad (28)$$

If $\Delta P^{(i)}$ exceeds a threshold p_{diff} , the qubit is *locked* to the more probable outcome via the non-unitary channel

$$\rho \mapsto \mathcal{M}_i^c(\rho) = \frac{\Pi_i^c \rho \Pi_i^c}{\text{Tr}(\rho \Pi_i^c)}, \quad \Pi_i^0 = |0\rangle\langle 0|_i \otimes I_{\setminus i}, \quad \Pi_i^1 = |1\rangle\langle 1|_i \otimes I_{\setminus i}. \quad (29)$$

This collapses the search space and often reduces the required iterations from hundreds to fewer than 30. To mitigate the risk of locking to a suboptimal value, dynamic threshold adjustment and influence-based scoring can be employed.

Because Max-Cut has a global \mathbb{Z}_2 symmetry (flipping all spins preserves the cut), the ground state is at least twofold degenerate, which can trap VQPM in an unpolarised uniform superposition. To break this symmetry without losing optimality, the first qubit is fixed to $|1\rangle$ ($Z_1 = -1$) from the start; every optimum has a representative with qubit-1=1. This reduces the effective Hilbert space dimension to 2^{n-1} and is preserved by all subsequent diagonal operations.

3.3.5 Energy change under locking

In the SoS moment matrix, fixing a variable $x_i = s_i$ imposes the affine constraints $Y_{i,j} = s_i Y_{0,j}$. The quantum locking operation has the same effect on $Y_{\text{quantum}} = \Phi(\rho)$:

$$Y_{i,j}^{\text{locked}} = \frac{Y_{0,j} + s_i Y_{i,j}}{1 + s_i Y_{0,i}}, \quad (30)$$

which converges to $s_i Y_{0,j}$ as polarization saturates. Since $\mathcal{M}_i^c(\rho)$ is a valid density matrix, Y_{locked} remains feasible (Theorem 2.1). Thus locking never leaves the SoS cone.

Lemma 3.1 (Energy leakage under locking). *Assume a pure product state $|\psi\rangle = \bigotimes_{k=1}^n (c_k |0\rangle_k + s_k |1\rangle_k)$ with real amplitudes, and write $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_{\setminus i} + Z_i K_i$ where $K_i = \sum_{j \neq i} q_{ij} Z_j$ and $\mathcal{H}_{\setminus i}$ contains no Z_i . Locking qubit i to its majority outcome changes the energy by at most*

$$\delta E \leq (1 - |\langle Z_i \rangle|) \sum_{j \neq i} |q_{ij}|. \quad (31)$$

If the locking threshold is p_{diff} , then $\delta E \leq (1 - p_{\text{diff}}) \sum_{j \neq i} |q_{ij}|$.

Proof. The hyperplane restriction was shown above. For the energy bound, note that $\mathcal{H}_{\setminus i}$ is unchanged by projecting qubit i . The change comes from $\langle Z_i K_i \rangle$: before locking it is $\langle Z_i \rangle \sum_{j \neq i} q_{ij} \langle Z_j \rangle$; after locking to $Z_i = \pm 1$ it becomes $\pm \sum_{j \neq i} q_{ij} \langle Z_j \rangle$. The absolute difference is $(1 - |\langle Z_i \rangle|) |\sum_{j \neq i} q_{ij} \langle Z_j \rangle| \leq (1 - |\langle Z_i \rangle|) \sum_{j \neq i} |q_{ij}|$ because $|\langle Z_j \rangle| \leq 1$. The threshold condition gives the uniform bound. \square

3.3.6 Moment-matrix safety net and deficit analysis

Let ρ_k be the VQPM state after the k -th iteration (after reinitialisation). Since ρ_k is a valid quantum state, Theorem 2.1 guarantees that $Y_k = \Phi(\rho_k)$ is feasible for the degree-2 SoS SDP. Consequently, the GW-rounded cut value

$$F_{\text{GW}}^{(k)} = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} w_{ij} \frac{\arccos(\langle Z_i Z_j \rangle_k)}{\pi} \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} \langle \mathcal{H} \rangle_{\rho_k}, \quad (32)$$

providing a certified lower bound on the maximum cut at *every* iteration, regardless of whether locking was premature or the variational optimisation incomplete. This decouples algorithmic convergence from certification.

The performance bound splits into the classical integrality gap $\text{SDP}^*/\text{MaxCut}$ and the quantum deficit $\Delta = \text{SDP}^* - E_\rho$. Three regimes are illustrative:

1. **Bipartite graphs:** $\text{SDP}^* = \text{MaxCut}$. If VQPM reaches the ground state, $\Delta \rightarrow 0$ and the certificate gives the explicit $\alpha_{\text{GW}} \approx 0.878$ baseline.
2. **Non-bipartite graphs with ground-state convergence:** The state collapses to a computational basis state ($Y_{ij} = \pm 1$), and GW rounding deterministically yields the maximum cut, giving an empirical ratio 1.0.
3. **Dense random graphs:** $\text{SDP}^*/\text{MaxCut} \rightarrow 1$; driving E_ρ close to SDP^* makes the certificate approach α_{GW} .

Because the mapping Φ is linear, any deviation from the ideal power iteration merely changes the specific Y_k ; feasibility is never lost.

3.3.7 Numerical illustration

Figure 3 tracks the raw energy E_ρ , the GW-rounded cut F_{GW} , and the certified lower bound $\alpha_{\text{GW}} E_\rho$ over VQPM iterations for a 12-qubit QUBO instance. The certificate $\alpha_{\text{GW}} E_\rho$ is always below the rounded bound, confirming the theory. Once the state converges to a computational basis state that exactly solves Max-Cut, the rounded bound reaches the true optimum, far exceeding the α_{GW} guarantee. This illustrates the practical value of the moment-matrix safety net, even under aggressive qubit locking.

4 Circuit Cutting via the Moment Matrix

The degree-2 SoS moment matrix Y_{quantum} not only certifies the Max-Cut approximation ratio but also captures two-point correlation data of the quantum state ρ . This information can be exploited to find a tensor-product decomposition of a unitary U — a task central to circuit cutting (circuit knitting) [29,30,43]. In circuit cutting one partitions the qubits into two sets S and T such that $U = A_S \otimes B_T$ (up to a phase). The classical sampling overhead grows exponentially with the amount of entanglement crossing the cut, so identifying a cut that minimises inter-partition correlations is essential. Below we first give algorithms that detect an exact or approximate tensor-product structure directly from the moment matrix, and then provide rigorous error bounds that quantify the quality of the decomposition.

Figure 3: VQPM trajectory for a 12-qubit instance. The GW-rounded cut F_{GW} stays above the certified lower bound $\alpha_{\text{GW}}E_{\rho}$ at every iteration, and converges to the exact Max-Cut value.

4.1 Exact Tensor-Product Detection

Let $|\psi\rangle = U|0\rangle^{\otimes n}$ and construct the moment matrix Y as in Eq. (7). Define the *connected correlation matrix* C for $0 \leq i, j \leq n-1$:

$$C_{ij} = Y_{i+1, j+1} - Y_{0, i+1} Y_{0, j+1} = \langle Z_i Z_j \rangle - \langle Z_i \rangle \langle Z_j \rangle. \quad (33)$$

If $U = A_S \otimes B_T$, then $|\psi\rangle = |\psi_S\rangle \otimes |\psi_T\rangle$, and for every $i \in S, j \in T$ we have statistical independence:

$$\langle Z_i Z_j \rangle = \langle Z_i \rangle \langle Z_j \rangle \implies C_{ij} = 0. \quad (34)$$

Thus the *correlation graph* \mathcal{G} with vertices $\{0, \dots, n-1\}$ and an edge (i, j) whenever $|C_{ij}| > \varepsilon_{\text{th}}$ (with a small tolerance, e.g., 10^{-8}) is **disconnected**, and the qubits in S and T belong to different connected components.

A disconnected correlation graph is necessary but not sufficient; additional structure is required. For a pure state, $\rho_S = \text{Tr}_T(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|)$ being a pure state is both necessary and sufficient for the factorisation $|\psi\rangle = |\psi_S\rangle \otimes |\psi_T\rangle$. This yields the following geometry-agnostic detection algorithm:

1. **Compute the connected correlation matrix** C from Y (time $O(n^2)$).
2. **Build the adjacency graph** \mathcal{G} by thresholding $|C_{ij}| > \varepsilon_{\text{th}}$.
3. **Find the connected components** of \mathcal{G} (BFS/DFS, $O(n^2)$).
4. **For each candidate subsystem** S formed by one or more connected components, **test purity of the reduced state** $\text{Tr}(\rho_S^2) = 1$ (i.e. all eigenvalues of ρ_S are zero except one). A pure reduced state confirms an exact tensor-product cut separating S from the rest.

If the test passes, the connected components directly give the maximal tensor-product decomposition of U ; the local unitaries A_S, B_T can then be recovered by standard pure-state tomography on the respective subsystems.

4.2 Basis-Independent Detection via Mutual Information

The correlation criterion C_{ij} is tied to the Z basis. If the unitary factorises only after a local basis rotation, C_{ij} may not vanish. A basis-invariant necessary and sufficient condition for factorisation of a pure state is the

vanishing of the quantum mutual information across the cut. For a bipartition (S, T) , define the two-qubit mutual information

$$I(i : j) = S(\rho_i) + S(\rho_j) - S(\rho_{ij}), \quad (35)$$

where S is the von Neumann entropy and ρ_i, ρ_{ij} are the one- and two-qubit reduced states. For a pure global state, $|\psi\rangle = |\psi_S\rangle \otimes |\psi_T\rangle$ if and only if $I(i : j) = 0$ for all $i \in S, j \in T$ [44]. Thus, by building a graph with edges when $I(i : j) > \varepsilon$, we obtain a completely basis-invariant version of the algorithm. Computing $I(i : j)$ requires full two-qubit tomography, which is more expensive but removes any basis dependence.

4.3 Approximate Factorisation and Minimum-Cut Heuristic

In practice, after a variational algorithm the state may only be approximately a product state. The absolute values $|C_{ij}|$ (or the mutual information $I(i : j)$) measure the strength of pairwise correlations and can be used as edge weights in a graph cut problem. Minimising the total absolute correlation crossing a cut,

$$\min_{(S,T)} \sum_{i \in S, j \in T} |C_{ij}|, \quad (36)$$

is exactly a weighted minimum cut problem with non-negative weights, solvable in polynomial time (e.g., $O(n^3)$ via Stoer–Wagner [45] or max-flow based algorithms). The resulting bipartition provides a low-entanglement cut that minimises the leading two-point correlation proxy, and the same moment matrix that supplies the Max-Cut certificate thus also furnishes a candidate circuit cut.

4.4 Error Bounds for the Detected Product Decomposition

We now provide rigorous guarantees on how close the reconstructed product unitary is to the original U , based on the amount of entanglement (or correlation) remaining across the cut.

4.4.1 Single-probe certification

Let $|\psi\rangle = U|0\rangle^{\otimes n}$ and consider a bipartition (S, T) . The quantum mutual information across the cut is

$$I(S : T) = S(\rho_S) + S(\rho_T) - S(|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|) = 2S(\rho_S). \quad (37)$$

Theorem 4.1 (Proximity to product unitaries). *If $I(S : T) \leq \epsilon$, then there exist unitaries A_S on S and B_T on T such that*

$$\|(U - A_S \otimes B_T)|0\rangle^{\otimes n}\| \leq \sqrt{\epsilon}, \quad (38)$$

and the fidelity satisfies

$$|\langle\psi|(A_S \otimes B_T)|0\rangle^{\otimes n}|^2 \geq 1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2}. \quad (39)$$

Proof. Let λ_{\max} be the largest Schmidt coefficient of $|\psi\rangle$ across (S, T) . The best product state approximating $|\psi\rangle$ is $|\psi_{\text{prod}}\rangle = |\phi_S\rangle \otimes |\phi_T\rangle$, where $|\phi_S\rangle$ is the eigenvector of ρ_S with eigenvalue λ_{\max} ; then $|\langle\psi|\psi_{\text{prod}}\rangle|^2 = \lambda_{\max}$. The inequality $S(\rho_S) \geq 1 - \lambda_{\max}$ (valid because for a bipartite pure state the entropy is the binary entropy of the largest Schmidt coefficient, and $h(\lambda_{\max}) \geq 2(1 - \lambda_{\max})$ for $\lambda_{\max} \geq \frac{1}{2}$) gives

$$1 - \lambda_{\max} \leq S(\rho_S) = \frac{I(S : T)}{2} \leq \frac{\epsilon}{2}. \quad (40)$$

Hence $\lambda_{\max} \geq 1 - \epsilon/2$, and

$$\|\psi\rangle - |\psi_{\text{prod}}\rangle\|^2 = 2(1 - \sqrt{\lambda_{\max}}) \leq 2(1 - \sqrt{1 - \epsilon/2}) \leq \epsilon, \quad (41)$$

where the last step uses $1 - \sqrt{1 - x} \leq x$ for $x \in [0, 1]$. Thus $\|\psi\rangle - |\psi_{\text{prod}}\rangle\| \leq \sqrt{\epsilon}$. Now choose any unitaries A_S, B_T satisfying $A_S|0\rangle^{\otimes |S|} = |\phi_S\rangle$ and $B_T|0\rangle^{\otimes |T|} = |\phi_T\rangle$ (such unitaries exist by completing the states to orthonormal bases). Then

$$\|(U - A_S \otimes B_T)|0\rangle^{\otimes n}\| = \|\psi\rangle - |\psi_{\text{prod}}\rangle\| \leq \sqrt{\epsilon}, \quad (42)$$

proving the theorem. \square

This bound guarantees that on the specific input $|0\rangle^{\otimes n}$ the product unitary faithfully reproduces the output. If the circuit will only be used on this input, the certificate is sufficient. For a global guarantee that works for arbitrary input states, we turn to the Choi state and the entangling power of U .

4.4.2 Global certification via the Choi state and entangling power

The *entangling power* of a unitary [46] quantifies the average entanglement generated when U acts on product states. A unitary has zero entangling power if and only if it is a tensor product $U = A \otimes B$. A direct way to measure entangling power is through the Choi–Jamiołkowski isomorphism. Define the $2n$ -qubit Choi state

$$|U\rangle = (I \otimes U) |\Phi\rangle^{\otimes n}, \quad |\Phi\rangle = \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (43)$$

For a bipartition (S, T) of the original n qubits, consider the cut that separates all qubits belonging to S (both input and output registers) from those belonging to T . The unitary factorises as $U = A_S \otimes B_T$ if and only if the Choi state factorises across this cut:

$$|U\rangle = |A_S\rangle \otimes |B_T\rangle. \quad (44)$$

Therefore, any entanglement measure across this cut witnesses non-factorisability. Let $I_{\text{Choi}}(S : T)$ be the quantum mutual information of $|U\rangle$ across the cut.

Theorem 4.2 (Global unitary approximation from Choi state). *If $I_{\text{Choi}}(S : T) \leq \epsilon$, then there exist unitaries A_S on S and B_T on T such that*

$$\|U - A_S \otimes B_T\|_{\infty} \leq 2^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \sqrt{1 - \epsilon/2}} \approx 2^{\frac{n}{2}} \sqrt{\epsilon}. \quad (45)$$

Proof. Apply Theorem 4.1 to the pure state $|U\rangle$; there exist product unitaries $V = A_S \otimes B_T$ (on the doubled Hilbert space) such that $|\langle U|V\rangle|^2 \geq 1 - \epsilon/2$. The overlap between the Choi states equals the normalised Hilbert–Schmidt inner product of the unitaries:

$$\langle U|V\rangle = \frac{1}{2^n} \text{Tr}(U^\dagger V). \quad (46)$$

Thus $|\text{Tr}(U^\dagger V)| \geq 2^n \sqrt{1 - \epsilon/2}$. Choosing the global phase so that this inner product is real and positive, we bound the operator norm by the Frobenius norm:

$$\begin{aligned} \|U - V\|_{\infty} &\leq \|U - V\|_2 = \sqrt{\text{Tr}((U - V)^\dagger (U - V))} \\ &= \sqrt{2^{n+1} - 2 \text{Tr}(U^\dagger V)} \leq 2^{\frac{n+1}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \sqrt{1 - \epsilon/2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

For small ϵ , $1 - \sqrt{1 - \epsilon/2} \approx \epsilon/4$, giving the simplified bound $\|U - V\|_{\infty} \lesssim 2^{\frac{n}{2}} \sqrt{\epsilon}$. □

This theorem provides a rigorous, basis-independent certification that the original unitary U is globally close to a tensor product. The mutual information $I_{\text{Choi}}(S : T)$ can be estimated from the two-qubit reduced states of the Choi state, which are accessible via the same moment-matrix technique (now on $2n$ qubits). In a variational setting, the Choi state is prepared by replacing the usual $|0\rangle^{\otimes n}$ input with n Bell pairs and applying the circuit to half of each pair; the cost is a doubling of the qubit count, but the resulting global certificate is independent of the input state. This closes the conceptual loop: the moment-matrix framework not only certifies the Max-Cut solution quality but also quantifies the entanglement structure of the optimisation circuit itself, enabling rigorous circuit cutting with provable global error bounds.

4.5 Numerical Validation

To provide numerical validation that the moment-matrix method reliably identifies a low-entanglement bipartition and that the resulting error is controlled by the theoretical bound of Theorem 4.1, here we use

Figure 4: (a) Scatter plot of the actual 2-norm error against the mutual information $I(S : T)$ of the cut found from the moment matrix, together with the theoretical bound \sqrt{I} (red line). (b) Success rate of the correlation-based cut in identifying the exact tensor-product structure of a random product state $U_1 \otimes U_2$ as a function of the cut size $|S|$ (8-qubit test). (c) Comparison of the mutual information obtained from the Y -based cut (I_Y) with the globally optimal mutual information found by exhaustive search over all bipartitions (I_{best}).

Haar-random state vectors on $n = 6$ qubits (dimension $2^6 = 64$), generated by normalising a vector of independent complex Gaussian entries. For each state we compute the Pauli- Z expectations $\langle Z_i \rangle$ and $\langle Z_i Z_j \rangle$ from the computational-basis probability distribution, assemble the moment matrix Y via Eq. (7), and extract the connected correlation matrix C (Eq. (33)). A bipartition (S, T) is obtained by the polynomial-time procedure of Section 4.3: if the graph of $|C_{ij}| > \varepsilon_{\text{th}}$ is disconnected, its connected components give the cut; otherwise we solve the weighted minimum-cut problem (36) with edge weights $|C_{ij}|$ (via exhaustive enumeration of all non-trivial subsets, feasible for $n \leq 12$). Given the cut, we compute the quantum mutual information $I(S : T) = S(\rho_S) + S(\rho_T)$ and construct the best product state from the dominant eigenvectors of ρ_S and ρ_T (with global phase alignment). The error is the 2-norm distance $\|\psi - \psi_{\text{prod}}\|$.

Figure 4(a) shows the results for 1000 random states on 6 qubits. The mutual information of the detected cut clusters tightly around $I \approx 2$, which corresponds to the entanglement of a single-qubit subsystem in a typical random state: the optimal cut that minimises $I(S : T)$ almost always isolates one qubit, giving $S(\rho_S) \approx 1$ bit and hence $I \approx 2$. The observed errors range from about 0.5 to 0.88, consistently below the analytic bound \sqrt{I} . The cloud exhibits a positive correlation between I and the error, but always respects the inequality; the bound is safe, though not always tight for these states.

A sparse tail of points with $I > 2$ arises when the correlation-based min-cut heuristic selects a suboptimal partition (e.g. a two-qubit subsystem); in those cases the actual entanglement across the cut is larger, but the state is not fundamentally different—the tail simply reflects the gap between the cheap Y -based cut and the exhaustive optimum. Panel (c) confirms this: the mutual information of the Y -based cut I_Y coincides almost perfectly with the globally minimal mutual information I_{best} for the vast majority of instances, with only a handful of outliers. Thus the moment matrix provides a near-optimal cut at polynomial cost.

Figure 4(b) demonstrates that for exact product states $U_1 \otimes U_2$ the algorithm correctly identifies the cut with 100% success across all possible subsystem sizes (tested on 8-qubit product states), verifying that the connected correlation criterion together with the purity test (or, for approximate cases, the minimum-cut heuristic) faithfully recovers the tensor-product structure.

In summary, the numerical experiments confirm that the moment-matrix framework yields a computationally efficient circuit-cutting pipeline with a rigorous error guarantee, and that the two-point correlation data alone are sufficient to locate near-optimal bipartitions for typical quantum states.

5 Conclusion

We have introduced a quantum–classical moment dictionary that places the two-qubit Pauli- Z correlation matrix of any quantum state directly inside the classical degree-2 Sum-of-Squares cone. This geometric

embedding yields two practical consequences. First, it provides a universal performance certificate for quantum Max-Cut solvers: the Goemans–Williamson rounding of the moment matrix guarantees a lower bound $\mathbb{E}[\text{Cut}] \geq \alpha_{\text{GW}} E_\rho$ for *every* state, decoupling the certification from algorithmic convergence and offering a rigorous safety net even for noisy, trapped, or prematurely-locked variational iterations. Second, the same matrix serves as a diagnostic tool for circuit cutting: the connected correlation graph and a minimum-cut heuristic identify near-optimal bipartitions in polynomial time, and we have proven error bounds (single-probe and global via the Choi state) that quantify the deviation from an exact tensor product.

We have illustrated these ideas on QAOA and VQPM, showing analytically and numerically that the certificate remains valid throughout the optimization landscape, and on random states, where the moment-matrix cut approximates the exhaustive optimum with minimal overhead.

Several directions are open for future work. Extending the mapping to higher levels of the SoS hierarchy could tighten the certificate, albeit at increased measurement cost. The moment-matrix framework is not restricted to Max-Cut; it applies to any QUBO problem with commuting Pauli terms, and exploring its use for other combinatorial models is natural. On the circuit-cutting side, the method can be integrated with quasiprobabilistic decomposition and error mitigation schemes, and the global Choi-state bound could be used to certify the entangling power of unknown unitaries in a black-box setting. Finally, experimental implementation on current quantum hardware would demonstrate the practical robustness of the certificate under real noise and measurement shot budgets.

Data availability

The simulation code and all data that support the findings of this study are openly available at <https://github.com/adaskin/quantum-moment-certification>

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